

Improvement of Motor and Sensory Neuron Survival with N-acetyl cysteine after Peripheral Nerve Injury

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Abstract

Background: Nerve transfers require for the donor nerve to be injured, either partially or completely, in order to guide regenerating axons into new targets. Axon regeneration and recovery after nerve grafting and transfer may be limited by retrograde neuronal death after injury. N-acetyl cysteine (NAC) and acetyl-L-carnitine (ALC) improve survival of neurons after adult nerve injury but it is unknown whether they improve survival after paediatric or neonatal injury when neurons are most susceptible to retrograde neuronal death. Our objective is to examine whether NAC or ALC treatment improves survival of neonatal motor or sensory neurons in a rat model of neonatal nerve injury.

Methods: Rat pups received either a sciatic nerve crush or transection injury at postnatal day 3 and were then randomized to receive either intraperitoneal vehicle (5% dextrose), NAC (750 mg/kg) or ALC (300 mg/kg) once or twice daily. Four weeks after injury, surviving neurons were retrograde-labeled with 4% Fluorogold. The lumbar spinal cord and L4/L5 dorsal root ganglia were then harvested and sectioned to count surviving motor and sensory neurons.

Results: Transection and crush injuries resulted in significant motor and sensory neuron loss, with transection injury resulting in significantly more retrograde neuron death. High-dose NAC (750 mg/kg twice daily) significantly increased motor neuron survival after neonatal sciatic nerve crush and transection injury. Neither NAC nor ALC treatment improved sensory neuron survival.

Conclusions: Proximal neonatal nerve injuries produce significant retrograde neuronal death after injury. Treatments improving motor and sensory neuron survival after nerve injury may improve recovery after nerve transfers or nerve grafting.

Keywords: N-acetyl cysteine, acetyl-L-carnitine, Proximal neonatal nerve

Introduction

Motor and sensory reconstruction with nerve grafts and nerve transfers provides a pathway to reinnervate tissue. However, redirecting axons down novel pathways first requires a partial or complete nerve injury in order to perform the coaptation and redirect regenerating axons. Peripheral nerve injuries are known to cause

substantial retrograde death of motor and sensory neurons in animal models (Stephen W.P. Kemp et al. 2015; Lowrie & Vrbová 1992), and this may contribute to limiting recovery after nerve repair. Untreated neuronal loss may severely limit the capacity for functional recovery, as the reduced number of neurons cannot fully reinnervate their denervated targets.

Several animal models, including rodents (Stephen W.P. Kemp et al. 2015; Lowrie & Vrbová 1992; Risling, Aldskogius, Hildebrand, et al. 1983; Carlson et al. 1979; Schmalbruch 1984; Schmalbruch 1987b), cats (Risling, Aldskogius & Hildebrand 1983; Carlson et al. 1979), and monkeys (Liss et al. 1996; Liss & Wiberg 1997), have demonstrated that neonatal motor and sensory neurons are profoundly sensitive to retrograde neuronal death following peripheral nerve injury, with loss of up to 80% of neurons (Schmalbruch 1984; Burls et al. 1991; Ekström et al. 1998; Ma et al. 2001; Rossiter et al. 1996). While retrograde neuronal death has not been definitively documented in human neonates, there is recent evidence of retrograde sensory neuron death following distal adult human peripheral nerve injury (West et al. 2013; Suzuki et al. 1993). Neurons are even more susceptible to retrograde neuronal death when injuries are proximal^{16,18,19}, occur at a young age^{11,12,17,20}, and following avulsion injury (Koliatsos et al. 1994; Fu & Gordon 1997; Ygge 1989; W. D. Snider et al. 1992; Li et al. 1998), making it likely that retrograde neuronal death also occurs following more proximal nerve transection injury.

After neonatal peripheral nerve injury, neuronal death is mostly apoptotic (Clowry et al. 1996; Lawson & Lowrie 1998; Bahadori et al. 2001; Chan et al. 2001; Rossiter et al. 1996) and occurs over a period of several days, providing an opportunity to intervene and prevent retrograde neuronal death (Burls et al. 1991; Lowrie et al. 1994). Cell death is triggered by the neurotoxic effects of injury and the loss of neurotrophic support derived from distal targets (Fu & Gordon 1997; Ambron & Walters 1996; Terenghi et al. 2011b). Improving motor and sensory neuron

survival after peripheral nerve injury improves functional recovery in a rat model (S.W.P. Kemp et al. 2015). Several agents, including neurotrophic factors (Sendtner et al. 1990; Clatterbuck et al. 1994; Yuan et al. 2000; Tan et al. 1996; Morcuende et al. 2013; Baumgartner & Shine 1998; Aszmann et al. 2002), NMDA-antagonists (Mentis et al. 1993; Greensmith et al. 1994; Dick et al. 1995; Nógrádi et al. 2007; Petsanis et al. 2012) and inhibitors of apoptosis (Sun et al. 1999; Chan et al. 2001; Chan et al. 2003) have been shown to improve neuronal survival following neonatal nerve injury. However, these compounds are either not approved for clinical use or have intolerable complications that would limit clinical translation.

N-acetyl cysteine (NAC) and acetyl-L-carnitine (ALC) increase the survival of motor and sensory neurons in adult animal models of ventral root rhizotomy and root avulsion (Zhang et al. 2005; Welin et al. 2009; Wilson et al. 2003). Both drugs are also approved for clinical use for other indications. NAC protects the liver in the context of acetaminophen toxicity and ALC is used to promote nerve regeneration in diabetic and chemotherapy-induced neuropathy (De Grandis 2007; Maestri et al. 2005; Chan et al. 2014). Both NAC and ALC have antioxidant properties, and both have been shown to decrease the expression of apoptotic proteins following injury (Reid et al. 2009; Barhwal et al. 2008). Neonatal motor and sensory neurons are significantly more susceptible to retrograde neuronal death than those of adults following peripheral nerve injury (Stephen W.P. Kemp et al. 2015; Lowrie & Vrbová 1992), and therefore, it remains unknown whether NAC and ALC increase motor and sensory neuron survival after neonatal peripheral nerve injury as well as adult nerve injury. If the agents are effective, they could be used clinically to prevent retrograde neuronal death after peripheral nerve injury.

In this study, we determined whether administration of NAC or ALC improves motor and/or sensory neuron survival in a neonatal rat model of peripheral nerve injury. We chose to investigate neuronal survival using both the standard neonatal sciatic nerve crush injury model and a transection injury model. Neonatal crush injury is the standard model for investigating retrograde neuronal survival (Stephen W.P. Kemp et al. 2015; Lowrie & Vrbová 1992); however, transection injury more accurately represents the clinical scenario of many nerve injuries, where meaningful nerve regeneration is not likely to occur without surgical repair (Bade et al. 2014; Chen et al. 2008).

Materials and Methods

Animals

Pregnant female Lewis rats (E118) were obtained from Charles River (Montreal, QC). Prior to study commencement, a statistical power analysis was done using G*Power 3.1 (Faul et al. 2007). Twelve rats were required per surgical paradigm (total of 48 animals amongst the four experiments) to detect a statistically significant difference with a Type I error of 0.05, power 0.9 and an expected effect size of 1.5. Depending on litter size, four to six rats were randomly assigned to each group (total n = 53). Each litter was randomized to include several treatment groups in order to control for variations in litters. At the time of injury, the neonatal rats weighed between 8-10 g. All rats were maintained in a temperature and humidity controlled environment with a 12:12 h light:dark cycle and the mother rats received *ad lib* water and standard rat chow (Purina, Mississauga, ON). Rat pups were kept with their mothers until study termination.

Surgical procedures were conducted in an aseptic manner with an operating microscope (Leitz, Willowdale, ON). Rats were sacrificed at study termination under deep anesthesia using intraperitoneal (i.p.) Euthanyl (sodium pentobarbital, 240 mg/mL concentration, 1 mL/kg, Bimeda-MTC, Cambridge, ON). These experiments were approved by The Hospital for Sick Children Laboratory Animal Services (LAS), which adheres to the guidelines of the Canadian Council on Animal Care.

Experimental Design

On post-natal day 3 (P3), neonatal rat pups were divided into one of three sciatic nerve injury groups: i) uninjured, ii) crush, and iii) transection without repair. Sciatic nerve injuries were performed on post-natal day 3 because significant retrograde motor neuron death occurs after neonatal sciatic nerve crush injury prior to post-natal day 5 only (Lowrie et al. 1994; Stephen W.P. Kemp et al. 2015). In each injury paradigm, rats were randomized (n = 53) to receive ani.p. injection of either vehicle (5% dextrose), N-acetyl cysteine (NAC) or acetyl-L-carnitine (ALC) immediately after surgery and then daily with a 30G syringe. Four to six neonatal rats were used per group.

In order to compare our results to previous work in our laboratory (S.W.P. Kemp et al. 2015), rats were treated for four weeks, at which point the rats were anesthetized and the sciatic nerve was re-exposed for retrograde-labeling on post-natal day 31 (P31). On post-natal day 34 (P34), three days after

retrograde labeling, rats were perfused with 4% paraformaldehyde and the lumbar spinal cord and L4/L5 dorsal root ganglia (DRGs) were harvested, sectioned and the retrograde labeled motor and sensory neurons counted.

NAC and ALC Administration

Following injury, rats were randomized (n = 53) to receive an i.p. injection of either vehicle (5% dextrose), N-acetyl cysteine (NAC) at a dose of 750 mg/ or acetyl-L-carnitine at a dose of 300 mg/kg (Sigma, Oakville, ON) immediately after surgery and then daily with a 30G syringe (Table 1). A separate group of rats were randomized to receive higher dose treatment with twice daily i.p. injections of NAC (750 mg/kg) and ALC (300 mg/kg) to investigate the effects of a two-fold higher dose (Table 2). The higher dose of NAC and ALC was administered as a twice daily injection as opposed to a single daily injection because of the limited volume that could be administer i.p per dose in neonatal rats.

The initial daily doses of NAC (750 mg/kg) and ALC (300 mg/kg) were determined based on previous studies in adult rats, demonstrating improved motor and sensory neuron survival with NAC (Hart et al. 2004; Welin et al. 2009) and improved sensory neuron survival with ALC (Karalija et al. 2012; Wilson et al. 2003; Wilson et al. 2007; Hart et al. 2002; Patel et al. 2010) at these doses. Higher dosing of both NAC and ALC was also investigated as neonatal neurons are profoundly more sensitive to retrograde neuronal death than adult neurons^{11,12,17,20} and therefore it was hypothesized that higher doses may be required.

Figure 1 Model of Neonatal Crush and Transection Injury.

The sciatic nerve was exposed through a midlateral incision and either crushed (A) or transected (B) distal to the quadratus femoris muscle. To prevent nerve regeneration after sciatic nerve transection, a suture (9-0 Nylon) was tied around the proximal transected stump and a portion of the distal nerve was excised

Surgical model of neonatal peripheral nerve injury

At postnatal day 3 (P3), rats were anesthetized using inhalational anesthetic (2% Isoflurane in 98% oxygen; Halocarbon Laboratories, River Edge, NJ). The right sciatic nerve was exposed through a lateral mid-thigh incision. In neonatal rats receiving a sciatic nerve crush injury, the sciatic nerve was crushed with a standard #5 jeweler's forceps for 30 s at the lower border of the quadratus femoris muscle (Figure 1A). As previously described (Stephen W.P. Kemp et al. 2015; S.W.P. Kemp et al. 2015), injuries were made in relation to the quadratus femoris muscle as this landmark was found to be more reliably discernable in neonatal rats than the trifurcation of the sciatic nerve. Complete sciatic nerve crush was confirmed by observing translucency in the section of nerve at the location of the crush.

For neonatal rats in which the sciatic nerve was transected, a 9-0 Nylon suture was tied around the sciatic nerve at the level of the quadratus femoris muscle and the nerve was then transected immediately distal to the suture (Figure 1B). The distal portion of the sciatic nerve was then removed to the level of the knee to ensure that regrowth of the transected nerve would not occur. Following surgery, all rat pups were returned to their home cages with their mothers, and were dosed for four weeks with either vehicle, NAC, or ALC as described previously. The pups received Metacam (0.3 mL/100 g body weight; Boehringer Ingelheim Vetmedica Inc., St. Joseph, MO) for post-operative pain relief.

Retrograde-labeling of surviving neurons

Retrograde labeling was performed four weeks following the initial surgery (at P31) to identify and count the surviving motor and sensory neurons (Catapano et al. 2016). A four week time point was used in order to compare our results to previous

results obtained in our lab with another neuroprotective pharmaceutical (S.W.P. Kemp et al. 2015). The right sciatic nerve was re-exposed through a mid-lateral thigh incision and transected 5 mm proximal to either the original crush site or the site of the nerve transection and ligation. To construct the petrotatum well, we first placed the petrotatum in a 1 mL syringe with a 25 gauge half-inch needle, which permitted accurate distribution of the petrotatum. The well was then constructed by placing two layers of petrotatum around the periphery of a small piece of plastic paraffin film (approximately

0.5 mm x 0.5 mm) adjacent to the transected nerve tip while ensuring that the nerve does not come in contact with the petrotatum as this may decrease labeling by preventing dye uptake. The proximal nerve stump was then carefully draped over the well so that the nerve tip was centered within the well and another layer of petrotatum was placed over the existing well walls to ensure no leakage occurred around the nerve. It was necessary to ensure that while the petrotatum was being placed that it came in contact with the Parafilm and nerve stump, otherwise leakage of the well occurred. The well was then filled with 10 μ L of 4% solution of FluoroGold (FG: Fluorochrome LLC, Denver, CO) dissolved in sterile saline solution and the nerve was left within the well for one hour, after which the well was removed and staining was confirmed visually by observing yellow staining of the exposed nerve tip. The proximal stump and wound were then rinsed three times with sterile saline to remove any residual dye and prevent staining of the adjacent muscle or nerve. Incisions were closed and, following recovery, animals were returned to their cages.

Counting of motor and sensory neurons

Three days following retrograde labeling on post-natal day 34 (P34), rats were euthanized using intraperitoneal Euthanyl (sodium pentobarbital, 240 mg/mL concentration, 1 mL/kg, Bimeda-MTC, Cambridge, ON) and perfused with 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA). The lumbar spinal cord and L4 and L5 DRGs were harvested and post-fixed in 4% PFA for one day and then cryoprotected in 30% sucrose in 4% PFA for four days prior to embedding in optimal cutting

temperature compound (OCT: Sakura Fine Technical Co., Torrance, CA). Spinal cords and DRGs were serially sectioned at 30 μ m and 20 μ m respectively, using a cryostat (Leica Microsystems Inc., Concord, ON) at -22° C and mounted onto Superfrost slides (Fisher Scientific, Ottawa, ON). Retrograde labeled motor and sensory neurons in each spinal cord section and every fifth DRG section respectively, were counted on a fluorescent microscope with a 10x objective (100x overall magnification; Leica). A blinded observer performed all counts. Correction for double counting was made using a correction factor, calculated as 0.48 by our laboratory using the method previously described (Abercrombie 1946).

Statistical analysis

All statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism® version 6.0 for Mac (GraphPad Software, Inc; San Diego, California). All data was analyzed using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with post-hoc Bonferroni correction applied, except for data in Figure 3A and 4C which was analyzed with a Student's t-test as animals treated with NAC were compared only with vehicle treated animals. Statistical significance was accepted at the level of $p < 0.05$; all data are expressed as the mean \pm SD.

Results

Neonatal nerve injury results in significant motor and sensory neuron loss

Retrograde labeling of the sciatic nerve in uninjured rats four weeks after birth identified 1160 ± 57 motor neurons and 4731 ± 218 sensory neurons in the rat lumbar spinal cord and L4 and L5 DRG respectively. Both sciatic nerve crush and transection injuries three days after birth resulted in significant reduction in the numbers of surviving motor and sensory neurons (Figure 2). Retrograde labeling 5 mm proximal to site of nerve injury four weeks after sciatic nerve crush injury demonstrated a 64% and a 48% reduction in the number of surviving motor and sensory neurons, respectively ($p < 0.001$). A neonatal sciatic nerve transection injury resulted in even greater neuronal loss, with retrograde labeling of the neurons identifying only 11% and 36% of motor and sensory neurons, respectively ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 2 Neuron Survival After Neonatal Nerve Injury.

There was a significant reduction in the numbers of (A) motor and (B) sensory neurons four weeks after both sciatic nerve crush and transection injuries in comparison to the uninjured sciatic nerve (** $p < 0.001$). Representative images of retrograde labeled motor neurons, in 50 μm longitudinal lumbosacral spinal cord sections, are shown for

(B) uninjured rat pups, and after (D) sciatic nerve crush, and (E) sciatic nerve transection injuries (bar is equal to 250 μm). The number of rats in each group and motor and sensory neuron counts are summarized in Table 1 and 2.

High-dose NAC significantly increases motor neuron survival after neonatal crush injury

Intraperitoneal (i.p) injection of NAC (1500 mg/kg) significantly improved motor neuron survival following neonatal crush injury in comparison to animals treated with vehicle or ALC ($p = .003$) (Table 1 and Fig. 3A). Treatment with a lower dose of NAC, with once daily i.p injection of NAC (750 mg/kg), had no significant effect on numbers of motor neurons that survived after neonatal sciatic nerve crush injury (Figure 3B). Treatment with i.p. injections of ALC (300 mg/kg) either once or twice daily also failed to promote motor neuron survival following crush injury (Figure 3A/B).

Figure 3 Treatment Twice Daily with NAC Increases Motor Neuron Survival following Nerve Crush.

(A) Intraperitoneal injection of NAC (750 mg/kg) twice daily following crush injury significantly increased motor neuron survival. (* $p < 0.05$) (B) Decreasing administration of NAC to once daily injection and treatment with ALC at either dose did not affect motor neuron survival. The number of animals in each group and motor and sensory neuron counts are summarized in Table 1 and 2.

Treatment with high-dose NAC significantly increases motor neuron survival after neonatal transection injury

Intraperitoneal (i.p) injection of NAC (1500 mg/kg) daily significantly improved motor neuron survival

in comparison to vehicle treated animals following neonatal transection injury ($p = 0.03$) (Table 2 and Fig. 4A). Once daily i.p. injection of NAC (750 mg/kg) did not significantly improve motor neuron survival following neonatal sciatic nerve transection injury (Figure 4B) and likewise, once daily i.p. injection of ALC (300 mg/kg) did not improve motor neuron survival (Fig 4B). In the transection injury model, the effect of twice daily injections of ALC on motor neuron survival was not investigated, as the same ALC dose had no effect on motor neuron survival after a less severe crush injury.

Figure 4 Motor Neuron Survival is Improved Following Transection injury with NAC.

(A) Treatment with NAC (750 mg/kg) twice daily increased motor neuron survival following sciatic nerve transection injury. (B) Decreasing administration of NAC to once daily injection and treatment with ALC at either dose did not increase motor neuron survival. The number of animals in each group and motor and sensory neuron counts are summarized in Table 1 and 2.

NAC and ALC do not improve sensory neuron survival after crush or transection injury

Following either neonatal sciatic nerve crush or transection injury, daily i.p. injection of either

NAC (750 mg/kg) or ALC (300 mg/kg) did not affect sensory neuron survival in comparison to rats treated with vehicle (Figure 5A/B). Increasing the daily dose of NAC, with i.p. injection of rats twice daily with NAC (1500 mg/kg) also failed to improve sensory neuron survival following neonatal sciatic crush or transection injury (Figure 5C/D). As for motor neuron survival in the crush injury model, the twice daily injections of ALC were not carried out because the twice daily injection of ALC (300 mg/kg) had no effect on the survival of sensory neurons after the less severe sciatic nerve crush injury.

Figure 5 Neither NAC nor ALC Improve Sensory Neuron Survival. Following neonatal sciatic nerve crush injury, neither NAC nor ALC improved sensory neuron survival when rats were treated with i.p. injections either (A) twice daily or (B) daily. While transection injury results in more retrograde sensory neuron death, neither NAC nor ALC improved sensory neuron survival when rats were treated either (C) twice daily or (D) daily. The number of animals in each group and motor and sensory neuron counts are summarized in Table 1 and 2.

Table 1 Motor and Sensory Neuron Survival After Neonatal Sciatic Nerve Crush Injury.

Values are mean ± STD. The number in each group is given in parenthesis.

Treatment	No. of MNs	% Survival of MN	No. of SNs	% Survival of SN
Uninjured	1160 ± 57 (6)		4731 ± 218 (6)	
Crush + dextrose	422 ± 144 (6)	36 ± 12.4	2463 ± 140 (6)	52 ± 3.0
Crush + ALC (300 mg/day)	467 ± 112 (6)	40 ± 9.7	2681 ± 181 (6)	57 ± 3.8
Crush + ALC (600 mg/day)	446 ± 121 (4)	38 ± 10.4	2441 ± 117 (4)	52 ± 2.5
Crush + NAC (750 mg/day)	494 ± 38 (6)	43 ± 3.3	2542 ± 305 (6)	54 ± 6.4
Crush + NAC (1500 mg/day)	755 ± 63 (4)	65 ± 5.4	2658 ± 370 (4)	56 ± 7.8

Table 2 Motor and Sensory Neuron Survival After Neonatal Sciatic Nerve Transection.

Values are mean ± STD. The number in each group is given in parenthesis.

Treatment	No. of MNs	% Survival of MN	No. of SNs	% Survival of SN
Uninjured	1160 ± 57 (6)		4731 ± 218 (6)	
Trans. + dextrose	132 ± 53 (6)	11 ± 4.6	1704 ± 200 (6)	36 ± 4.2
Trans. + ALC (300 mg/day)	129 ± 80 (5)	11 ± 6.9	1889 ± 524 (5)	40 ± 11.1
Trans. + NAC (750 mg/day)	150 ± 39 (6)	13 ± 3.4	2088 ± 468 (6)	44 ± 9.9
Trans. + NAC (1500 mg/day)	241 ± 65 (4)	21 ± 5.6	1794 ± 287 (4)	38 ± 6.1

High-dose NAC resulted in significant weight loss

Rat pups treated with high-dose NAC gained significantly less weight by the time of sacrifice at post-natal day 33 than littermates treated with vehicle ($80 \text{ g} \pm 5$ vs 94 ± 9 ; $p < 0.001$) (Figure 6A). Differences in weight were greatest at 34 days and most apparent when rats were separated into subgroups of male and female rat pups (Figure 6B). When analysed separately, male rats treated with high-dose NAC gained approximately 22 g less of weight in comparison to littermates treated with

vehicle by the date of sacrifice (P34) ($83 \text{ g} \pm 5$ vs 104 ± 3 ; $p < 0.001$). Likewise, female rats treated with high-dose NAC also gained approximately 12 g less weight than littermates treated with vehicle by the date of sacrifice (P34) ($77 \text{ g} \pm 4$ vs 89 ± 4 ; $p < 0.001$). Rat pups treated with lower doses of NAC or ALC exhibited no differences in weight gain in comparison to littermates treated with vehicle (data not shown). Through observation, all rats treated with high-dose NAC also appeared more lethargic and relatively underdeveloped in comparison to littermates although this difference was not investigated further or quantified.

Figure 6 Animals Treated with High-dose NAC Gained Less Weight.

After both crush and transection neonatal nerve injury, rat pups treated with high-dose NAC demonstrated less weight gain than littermates treated with vehicle. These differences were statistically different over time when compared with repeated measures ANOVA ($p < 0.001$). When analyzed separately as male and female subgroups, both male and female rats were significantly lighter at the date of sacrifice (P 34) in comparison to vehicle treated littermates ($p < 0.001$).

Discussion

We found that high-dose N-acetyl cysteine (NAC), when administered twice daily, significantly increased motor neuron survival after both sciatic nerve crush and transection injuries in neonatal rats. This is consistent with findings of improved motor neuron survival with NAC treatment in adult models of peripheral nerve injury (Zhang et al. 2005; Karalija et al. 2012). However, much higher doses (1500 mg/kg/d as compared to 750mg/kg/d) were required to protect injured motor neurons in neonatal rats in our study. In contrast, we also found that both NAC and acetyl-L- carnitine (ALC) were ineffective at reducing sensory neuron death after neonatal peripheral nerve injury.

This contrasts previous work in adult models of peripheral nerve injury, where both NAC (Hart et al. 2004; Welin et al. 2009) and ALC (Karalija et

al. 2012; Wilson et al. 2003; Wilson et al. 2007; Hart et al. 2002) improved sensory neuron survival and once-daily dosing of NAC improved motor neuron survival (Zhang et al. 2005). Neonatal neurons are profoundly more sensitive to retrograde neuronal death than adult neurons^{11,12,17,20}, and, therefore, higher doses of NAC and ALC may be required to improve motor and sensory neuron survival after neonatal nerve injuries. In adult models of peripheral nerve injury, higher doses NAC are more effective at improving motor neuron survival after ventral rhizotomy and avulsion injuries, and the same has been shown for ALC, with higher treatment doses demonstrating more effective protection of adult sensory neurons (Zhang et al. 2005; Wilson et al. 2003). In our study, NAC treatment after neonatal peripheral nerve injury improved only motor neuron survival and not sensory neuron survival, which may be due to differences in sensitivity of motor and sensory neurons to retrograde neuronal death after injury (Lewis et al. 1999; Benn et al. 2002).

In addition to NAC, several other agents have also demonstrated improvement in motor neuron survival following neonatal peripheral nerve injury. These include inhibitors of glutamate- induced excitotoxicity (Mentis et al. 1993; Greensmith et al. 1994; Dick et al. 1995; Nógrádi et al. 2007; Petsanis et al. 2012), neurotrophic factors (Sendtner et al. 1990; Clatterbuck et al. 1994; Yuan et al. 2000; Tan et al. 1996; Morcuende et al. 2013;

Baumgartner & Shine 1998; Aszmann et al. 2002), and inhibitors of apoptosis (Sun et al. 1999; Chan et al. 2001; Chan et al. 2003). While several of these agents are more potent than NAC in protecting neonatal motor neurons from neuronal death, none of these agents are approved for use in humans, in part because possible adverse effects on development have not been determined.

While N-acetyl cysteine has a long history of safe use clinically in patients with cystic fibrosis and acetaminophen toxicity, we found that treatment with high-dose NAC (1500 mg/kg/day) resulted in significantly less weight gain than neonatal rat pups treated with low-dose NAC (750 mg/kg/day), ALC or vehicle. NAC (1500 mg/kg/day) treated rat pups also appeared more lethargic when examined. For acetaminophen toxicity, N-acetyl cysteine is used at much lower doses (300 mg/kg) for a shorter period of time (24 hours) and is known to result in anaphylactoid reactions. Severe systemic adverse reactions have been also been reported with NAC following iatrogenic overdose (Mahmoudi et al. 2015; Sandilands & Bateman 2009). Toxicity in rats with high-dose NAC has been shown in other studies, however the mechanism remains unknown (Sprong et al. 1998). Animal studies have

suggested that high-doses (1200 mg/kg/day) may decrease hepatic glucose metabolism and impair liver regeneration, which both may adversely affect growth (Yang et al. 2009; Zwingmann & Bilodeau 2006). Given these findings, further investigation into the side effects of long-term high-dose NAC treatment is required prior to the clinical translation of these results.

Given recent findings in adults (West et al. 2013; Suzuki et al. 1993), it is highly likely that retrograde death of motor and sensory neurons is an overlooked component of disability following peripheral nerve injury. Neuronal death may limit functional recovery following nerve injuries and surgical repair. N-acetyl cysteine (NAC) is an attractive agent for clinical translation as it is already approved for clinical use in neonates for other indications. However, further investigation into other treatment strategies, such as localized drug delivery systems or more frequent dosing regimens, is required. This may limit systemic toxicity of NAC while still providing motor neurons with high enough doses to prevent retrograde neuronal death (Wood et al. 2013; Zhang et al. 2005).

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